

NEW ENERGY SOURCES SU(6) & SU(12)

Dr Narayan Kumar Bhadra

Email: narayan102010@gmail.com

Lakshmipur Swamiji Seva Sangh High School Laskhmipur,
Gobardanga, 24 Parganas(N), West Bengal, India.

In quantum theories of consciousness, it is suggested that consciousness is a fundamental property of the universe. Our physical universe appeared by the phase-like transition of the energy groups from Big-Rip singularity. There are three stages of energies \rightarrow before 10 dimensional universe – (10-7) dimensional flat universe – then closed universe (as like “Gas – Vapor - Liquid). Before the explanation of the groups SU(23), SU(11) and SU(5), we give an example, such as, the change of state of a matter, it is required latent heat, but this latent heat can't be measured by any instrument but its existence can't be ignored at any cost. As such when in the liquid state the energy of the group SU(5) changes to the ultimate reality of the group of energy SU(11), in the vapor state, there must exist another type of energy group SU(6) like latent heat, its name may be given as „intelligence“, which are responsible for the acceleration of the energy of SU(5).and also the cause for the creation of D. N. A. of the live body etc.

The human brain and its mental aspects are associated with classical brain physiology and are also part of a quantum physical universe. Using the “lie algebra”, it was shown that our universe started with the symmetry breaking of the Gaussian energy group SU(11). The above stated three phases for our physical universe, the last class of unified symmetry groups can be expressed mathematically as $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$; $SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$ & $SU(5) \supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$. That means $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(6) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$. “Consciousness” created by the electromagnetic forces in the framework of $SU(12) \times U(1)$ & $SU(6) \times U(1)$...so on, whereas “Mind” created by the framework of $SU(2) \times U(1)$. The human brain conceived as an interfacing organ that not only produces mind and consciousness but also receives information. The brain or parts of the brain are conceived as an *interference hologram* of incoming data and already existing data (a “personal universe”) which equivalent to the subject's memory. If properly exposed (“analyzed”), information about the outer world can be distilled where “analyzer” is cerebral electrophysiology.

I. New Energy Source SU(6)

. In the transformations under the group SU(6), the basic fields here are the latent energy field and we have $U = \exp(-iH) \dots\dots\dots (1)$. Where H is a 6×6 Hermitian matrix of zero trace. We have 35 matrix charges $I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots\dots\dots I_{35}$ out of which five matrices are diagonal corresponding to this, we have 35 bosons. For want of any specific designation, they are referred to simply as J_k . There were no change takes place for exchanging the bosons namely $J_{k3}, J_{k8}, J_{k15}, J_{k24}, J_{k35}$, corresponding to the said five diagonal matrices. We expect the participating interactions of the bosons J_k to have comparable strength. The J_k bosons are expected to generate a latent force. This force is believed to be potentially so large that the exotic matter fluid are expected to transfer into the ordinary matter and then everything of the universe.

II. Super Unified Theory SU(11)

It can be expected, that for the symmetry breaking of SU(11), created an amount of positive energy, negative energy and an equivalent amount of latent energy.

III. Super Unified Field: SU (23)

In the theory of Gauss transformation in physics, the special unitary group is used to represent bosonic symmetries. In the theories of symmetry breaking, it is important to find the subgroups of special unitary group. Important subgroups of SU(n) that are important in GUT physics(also in the present dissertation). Super unified theory is

$$\text{For } p > 1, n-p > 1 \text{ with } \text{SU}(n) \supset \text{SU}(p) \times \text{SU}(n-p) \times \text{U}(1).$$

For completeness there are also the orthogonal and symplectic subgroup: $\text{SU}(n) \supset \text{O}(n)$; $\text{SU}(2n) \supset \text{USp}(2n)$

Since the rank of SU(n) is n-1 and U(1) is 1, a useful check is that the sum of the ranks of the subgroups is less than or equal to the rank of original group SU(n) which is a subgroup of various other lie group : $\text{SO}(2n) \supset \text{SU}(n)$.

From the symmetry breaking of SU(23), we find SU(12) and SU(11) as the subgroups of SU(23), where $p (= 11) > 1$; $n-p (= 23-11 = 12) > 1$, so that $\text{SU}(n) \supset \text{SU}(p) \times \text{SU}(n-p) \times \text{U}(1)$. i.e. $\text{SU}(23) \supset \text{SU}(12) \times \text{SU}(11) \times \text{U}(1)$. For completeness there are also the orthogonal and symplectic subgroups:

$$\text{SU}(23) \supset \text{O}(23) ; \text{SU}(46) \supset \text{USp}(46).$$

Since the rank of SU (23) is 22 and U(1) is 1, a useful check is that the sum of the ranks of the subgroup SU(12) and SU(11) is less than or equal to the rank of the original group. Thus, we have from SU(23), the Hermitian matrix H has 528 arbitrary constants. Which correspond to 528 bosons that now mediate between the different basic entities. Of these we already have 143 from SU(12) and 120 from SU(11) and 1 from U(1).

Thus, $528 - (143 + 120 + 1) = 264$ more bosons are needed to make up the list of 528. For want of any specific designation, they are referred to simply as the \mathbf{J}_N bosons. The \mathbf{J}_N bosons are expected to link the participants of SU(12) with SU(11) i.e. with SU(6), SU(5) and hence SU(2), SU(3) and U(1). There are emitted and absorbed $\bar{\mathbf{J}}_N$ particles (anti \mathbf{J}_N particles). Therefore, in the theory of SU (23), it is possible to change any of 132 (one hundred and thirty two) latent energy bosons of SU(12) into any of the 132 (one hundred and thirty two) bosons of SU(11) or vice-versa by the exchange of the \mathbf{J}_N -bosons of SU(23). So at this stage, by the symmetry breaking of SU(23) an amount of energy of SU(11) created for our universe, by the energy group SU(12).

IV. New Energy Source: SU(12)

In the transformations under the energy group SU(12), the basic fields here are the latent energy field and we have

$$U = \exp (- iH),$$

Where 'H' is a 12×12 Hermitian matrix of zero-trace. The matrix H now has 143 independent components. In the weak interaction SU(2), we have, H has 2×2 Hermitian matrix of zero-trace and the most general form of such matrix is

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{a} & \mathbf{b+ic} \\ \mathbf{b-ic} & -\mathbf{a} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{a} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{1} \end{pmatrix} + \mathbf{b} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{1} \\ \mathbf{1} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} + \mathbf{c} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{i} \\ -\mathbf{i} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus, like above, we have 143 matrix charges $I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{143}$. Corresponding to this, we have 143 bosons. For want of any specific designation, they are referred to simply as \mathbf{J}_{kn} . We expect the participating interactions of the bosons \mathbf{J}_{kn} to have comparable strength. The \mathbf{J}_{kn} bosons are expected to

generate a latent force. This force is believed to be potentially so large that the energy like as gas are expected to transfer into the energy like vapor for the construction of our universe.

In the same process, we can explain the consciousness of the energy group SU(24) and super unified field SU(47) etc. and so on, up-to the Big-Rip singularity.

V. Our Physical Universe.

There is no consensus yet on how the universe initially came to be, the general assumption is that perhaps an energetic fluctuation caused the universe to tunnel into the existence from quantum foam. The question of why the large energy of the universe is in a dark, i.e. not found in practical, the observed vacuum energy is so small in comparison to the scales of particle physics is known as cosmological constant problem. It is generally thought to be easier to imagine an unknown mechanism which would set vacuum parameter exactly to zero and so it can be considered that there exist several unifications from the very beginning of the universe i.e. from Big-Rip singularity. This class of symmetry group can be expressed mathematically as $SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$; $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$; $SU(47) \supset SU(24) \times SU(23) \times U(1)$;so on. We can assume SU(5) as matter energy group and SU(6) a new type of energy sources may be called as latent energy group together which changes into the energy group SU(11) [similarly, apply for SU(23); SU(47) etc.], i.e. to the super unified group. So, it is considered that the breakdown of SUT (Super Unified Theory) symmetry group SU(11), breaks into two fundamental groups $SU(5) \times SU(6)$ leads to a phase transition and then the fundamental group SU(5) which also breaks into subgroups $SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$, in which the scalar field Φ changes. The original vacuum, i.e. false vacuum ($\Phi = \sigma$) is no longer the true vacuum ($\Phi = 0$). The inflationary stage arises, however, if the true vacuum is not immediately attained. It seems our universe emerged from infinity to the universe of the energy group SU(11), a special unitary group having 11×11 matrices, such that $SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$. Thus, we have from SU(11), the Hermitian matrix H has 120 arbitrary constants. Which correspond to 120 bosons that now mediate between the different basic entities, of these we already have 60-bosons from the matter energy group SU(5), latent energy group SU(6) and from U(1). Thus, $120 - (24 + 35 + 1) = 60$ more bosons are namely J-bosons are expected to link the participants of SU(6) with SU(5). Therefore, in the theory of SU(11), it is possible to change any of 30 (thirty) latent energy bosons of SU(6) into any of the 30(thirty) matter energy bosons of SU(5) or vice-versa by the exchange of the J-boson. That is why it becomes possible to create or destroy matter particles and hence the universe seems to appear from nothing.

The class of symmetry group from Big-Rip singularity can be expressed mathematically as follows: $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$; $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$; $SU(47) \supset SU(24) \times SU(23) \times U(1)$;.....so on. Thus we have, $SU(12n-1) \supset SU(6n) \times SU(6n-1) \times U(1)$, where, $n = 2^0, 2^1, 2^2, 2^3, 2^4, \dots, \infty$. i.e. $SU(12n-1) \supset SU(6n) \times \dots \times SU(24) \times SU(12) \times SU(6) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$. So, according to the laws of symmetry breaking of the Gaussian energy group, there exists neither any Big-Bang nor any Big-Crunch singularity, only there Big-Rip singularity and Big-Break-singularity (DETAILS IN MY ARTICLE "THE COMPLEX QUANTUM AND CLASSICAL PSEUDO-TACHYONIC UNIVERSE"). All the dark energies mainly SU(12), SU(24), etc. are also responsible for the various consciousness and intelligence of the living cells or bodies according to the progress for biological revolution as such the progress of the material universe depends on the sub-energy groups of $SU(5) \supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$ stated by the standard model of physics. Again the activities of the energy groups for consciousness are restricted to unfold for each galaxy of the universe as well as for every solar system of the galaxies. The quantum universe actually started from Big-Rip singularity where energy pressure and densities simultaneously exists.

VI. Double Slit Experiments

Double slit experimental theorem may explained by the series of new energy sources SU(6), SU(12),etc. The existences of the new energy sources established but not being observed by an observer practically. Our 4-dimensional matter universe observed if there was created a "whole", like single slit open i.e. by the symmetry breaking of the unified group SU(5) and creates a shower of photons & quanta of the matter particles on the natural screen of the universe or otherwise like double slits open from the 10-dimensional space-times photons & quanta by the new energy sources of SU(6) emitted as 'knew' [i.e. the symmetry breaking of the super-unified energy group SU(11) and then SU(5)], we found an entangled-like matter energy with spirit energy by SU(6). It was compared with a situation of the universe where relatively very lower energy density in the ocean of the new energy

sources in one phase, starting from Big-Rip singularity like as in the gaseous phase and then vapor & liquid phase. It is observed from the Einstein's space-time theory, that means we have from the Friedmann equation for the evolution of the cosmic scale factor $R(t)$ which represents the size of the universe, is found at a finite time in the past R must have been equal to zero. Then the contents of all the galaxies must have once been squeezed together in a small volume i.e. numerically, the volume of the matter universe once been squeezed in a zero volume. We may assume that the matter universe is then transferred into another phase by the phase-like transition system with the help of latent energy group $SU(6)$ [$SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$]. The subgroup $SU(6)$ has been interpreted as a new type of energy sources other than $SU(5)$ [$SU(5) \supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$], the standard model of physics. So there were several environmental atmospheric situations, according to the unified group $SU(11)$, $SU(23)$ ∞ etc. all belongs to the Einstein's so called "nothing". Thus we assumed our physical universe appeared from something instead of nothing. It was discussed in my previous article that the quantum behaviour having some classical counterpart that can always choose such a quantum state, which does not disappear at any value of R_I , which guarantees the positivity of the quantum average of the operator. Coming back to our cosmological model we can say that the requirements of the well-definiteness of the pseudo-tachyonic part of the Hamiltonian operator in the Wheeler-DeWitt equation, does not imply the disappearance of the wave function of the universe at some values of the variables and thus, does not reveal the effect of the quantum avoidance of the cosmological singularity.

The strength of weak force gradually decreases and the strength of strong force increases as we advanced from the symmetry breaking of the unified group $SU(5)$. The first stage of the formation of our universe from so called nothing which was basically from non-locality to locality by the symmetry breaking of the Super Unified energy group $SU(11)$, where the energy group $SU(6)$ remains latent in the present and behaving like as consciousness in the framework of $SU(6) \times U(1)$ creating an electromagnetic force called spirit stuff. The bosons of the energy group $SU(6)$ always controlled all measurable energies of $SU(5)$ including 'quarks' & 'leptons' etc. and specially produces a strong neutral current which are applicable within a 'live' cells/elements/animals/plants etc. with an electromagnetic interaction created by $SU(2)$ with $U(1)$ in the frame-work of $SU(2) \times U(1)$ etc. called "Mind" (the physical stuff), again from $SU(5)$ we found matter energies, fermions, charge particles, spin, etc. like the decomposes of water by applying electric charges (extra energy) connecting with an electric circuit, we get hydrogen, oxygen as charged particles primarily and then gases with different characters from the characters of water. But the two gases, hydrogen & oxygen may again react with each other at some situation and get water having no characters either of Hydrogen or Oxygen. It is very interesting that the generated hydrogen and oxygen from water can be reacted with other chemical elements in some situations and found different characters in different forms. So, we consider, there exists two phases of the universe, (1) local, that means, matter particles produces the requirements from the first phase of non locality, i.e. as per the requirements of our universe also maintaining the law of wave-particle duality theorem (called mind) and (2) non local, i.e. particles remained in the wave form (called spirit), produces in the first phase of our universe which controlled the second phase, our physical universe.

All the symmetry breakings from infinite space-time [i.e. Big-Rip singularity] to Big-Bang belong to the first phase, called pseudo-tachyonic universe. Thus all the pseudo-energy groups from infinities are dominantly controlled ourselves while the energy group $SU(6)$ are directly controls the whole universe including ourselves, also created consciousness or intelligence and others like emotions etc. So, by the quanta with the strong forces of $SU(6)$ within the environmental situations of $SU(11)$ where 30-bosons of $SU(6)$ changes to the 30-bosons of $SU(5)$ or vice-versa, unfolded the physical universe and then we found everything of our universe. It is a continuous process from infinitely discrete universe.

VII. Comparison between Robot Brain and Human Brain.

I, agree with Eugene Wigner's (see Wigner, 1992) suggestion that it is consciousness that collapses the wave function, as stated by Penrose and that the collapse of a special (objective) type of wave function produces consciousness.

It is helpful to have a conceptual picture of quantum superposition in a super gravitational context that means in the super-unified theory(SUT) of $SU(11)$ [$\supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$], where the energy group $SU(6)$ created gravitational field. According to modern accepted physical theories, reality is rooted in 3-dimensional space and a 1-dimensional time, combined together into a 4-dimensional space–time. But here we consider that the origin of reality is rooted in $(4 + D)$ –dimensional Friedmann–Robertson–Walker type universe having complex scale factor $\mathbf{R} + i\mathbf{R}_1$, where \mathbf{R} is the scale factor corresponding to the usual 4–dimensional Universe while \mathbf{R}_1 is that of D –dimensional space. According to the new theories our actual reality of the so called material universe is rooted in 10-dimensional space-time instead of 4-dimensional space-time.

It is now well known that superconductivity and other large-scale quantum effects can actually occur at temperatures very far from absolute zero.

It is very convenient to say about the participation of the neutral current occurs in the frame-work of the super-unified group $SU(11)$ [$\supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$], i.e. specially in the frame-work $SU(6) \times U(1)$, where $SU(6)$ having 35-bosons, out of which five bosons namely $\mathbf{J}_{K3}, \mathbf{J}_{K8}, \mathbf{J}_{K15}, \mathbf{J}_{K24}, \mathbf{J}_{K35}$, corresponding to the five diagonal matrices. The strong neutral current created by $SU(6)$ with $U(1)$ are likely to be compared with the weak neutral current created by the framework of $SU(2)$ with $U(1)$ of the unified group $SU(5)$ [$\supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$], where $SU(2)$ does not directly involve with electric, it still seems to demand charged bosons \mathbf{W}_1 and \mathbf{W}_2 . This circumstances prompted efforts to link it with an electromagnetic interaction. This link achieved via $SU(2) \times U(1)$ frame-work originally proposed by A. Salam and S. Weinberg and sometimes called the electro-weak interaction. The link brings the photon (which is a boson), closer to three particles $\mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{W}_2$ & \mathbf{W}_3 , where $\mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{W}_2$ are two opposite charged particles and the third (\mathbf{W}_3) neutral. In this unified picture it is more convenient to say that another neutral particle \mathbf{Z}^0 instead of $\mathbf{W}_3, \mathbf{Z}^0$ has zero mass and charge, just like the photon. However, the photon does not interact with the neutrino while the \mathbf{Z}^0 does. The exchange of \mathbf{Z}^0 does not alter electric charge, and hence such an interaction is called a neutral current interaction. Similarly, if we go beyond the standard model of physics i.e. in the symmetry theory of $SU(11)$, we see there are five neutral particles of the latent energy group $SU(6)$, in which two pairs, namely $\mathbf{J}_{K3}, \mathbf{J}_{K8}$ and $\mathbf{J}_{K15}, \mathbf{J}_{K24}$ were interchanged without any colour changes, but the neutral particle \mathbf{J}_{K35} , like as \mathbf{Z}^0 also create a strong neutral current as $SU(6)$ is very strong i.e. electromagnetic interaction through the frame-work $SU(6) \times U(1)$, called pseudo-electromagnetic interaction which may responsible for the consciousness sensory with material weak electromagnetic interaction achieved by the frame-work of $SU(2) \times U(1)$. We observe that, towards unification of $SU(3), SU(2), U(1)$, the strength of weak force gradually increases while strength of strong force gradually decreases and ultimately we found the unified group $SU(5)$. So, in the theory of $SU(11)$ i.e. in another phase we found quark-like & lepton-like particles, which may be five times of each quark [i.e. u-quark, d-quark,.....etc. of the standard model of physics of the unified group $SU(5)$] or each of five different quarks [namely, $\{\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2, \dots, \mathbf{u}_5\}$ -quarks, $\{\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \dots, \mathbf{d}_5\}$ -quarks,....etc.]. Thus \mathbf{Z}^0 - like neutral particle of $SU(6)$ like zero mass & charges instead of \mathbf{J}_{K35} interact with other particles of $SU(5)$ creating strong neutral current with conscious sensory information system.

In the theoretical physics, we observe the flavour-changing neutral current (FCNC's) are hypothetical expressions that change the flavour of a fermions current without altering its electric charge. If they occur in nature (as reflected by Lagrangian interaction terms) these processes may induce phenomena that have not yet been observed in experiment. Flavour-changing neutral currents may occur in the standard model beyond the tree level, but they are highly suppressed by the GIM mechanism. FCNC's are generally predicted by theories that attempt to go beyond the standard model, such as the models of Super-Symmetry or Technicolor. Their suppression is necessary for an agreement with observations, making FCNC's important in model-building. The Cemi-field theory conceives that the electromagnetic field in the brain fine tunes the probabilities of neuron firings. The affected neurons may be a part of the larger connected assemblies, and this leads to memory and learning. In simulated networks non-synaptic neuronal interactions via the electromagnetic field and also gap junctions enhance learning. Modulation of long term potentiating by electromagnetic fields has also been demonstrated in vitro in rat hippocampus slices.

I.

VIII. Photon and Electric Charge-Mediated Consciousness

The change of a larger group $SU(11)$ of symmetries to the subgroup $SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$ is spontaneous by the redistribution of energy particles of stages like gaseous as explained before. The above subgroup which contained the $U(1)$ group, there inevitably arises particles (whose annihilation formed charge particles) that have the

characteristics like a magnetic mono-pole. Typically, the mass of which (in energy units) may be $\sim 10^{19}$ Gev (Plank energy). Monopoles like charge particles are highly stable particles and once created are not destructible. And so they would survive as relics to the present epoch. The explanation of the two energy groups SU(5) and SU(6) of the SUT energy group SU(11), we begin with the analogy of ferromagnetism and crucial role of the Curie-temperature (770°C for iron). Above this temperature a bar of iron shows no magnetism in an external field. This is because its elementary nuclear magnets are randomly aligned with no resultant magnetization. Energetically, this is the lowest state for the bar and it chooses to remain in that state as the most stable one. Below the Curie temperature the state of lowest energy changes to that in which all the nuclei are aligned along the bar, which develops polarity at its ends. There are two states of the same lowest energy possible, depending on which (north or south) of the two poles falls at a given end. The ultimate choice of one state apparently breaks symmetry although theoretically and inherently the symmetry is always there. In the early universe something similar happened to the super unified theory SU(11) and then SU(5). Above like a critical temperature T_c , the vacuum state, the state of lowest energy, is none other than the potential $\phi = 0$. Below T_c , the states of lowest energy of the thermo-statistical particles are changed. It now corresponds to a situation when ϕ has non-zero values. Corresponding to states of the same lowest energy, let us suppose that there exist alternative values ϕ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) which now acquire that status of vacuum. There were basic symmetry with respect to all ϕ_i , but in practice the system may spontaneously acquire one of them. This is again an apparent break-down of the symmetry. The consequences of this for the very early universe are that it is divided into different domains, each with a different value of ϕ_i . In this way the universe acquires discontinuities along the domain walls. These translate into highly significant discontinuities of matter distribution. The fact that we do not see such discontinuities in actuality (say in the form of large sheets of matter) is hard to explain away. This difficulty is known as the domain wall problem. The intersection of two domain walls is a linear structure known as “cosmic-string” such filamentary structure have been invoked in scenarios for galaxy form.

IX. Conclusion

Quantum physics indicates that consciousness is related to the awareness that an electron appears to show in the wave/particle duality (double slit experiment). Quantum physicists have shown that the electron behaves differently when being observed by a human. When the electron is not being observed, the electron behaves like a wave, but when an observing instrument is placed in the experiment, the electron behaves like a particle. This experience indicates that the electron will change its behaviour/reality depending on whether or not the electron is being observed as if the electron is aware that it is being observed. This awareness is very similar, if not the same, as human awareness and may be related to the same consciousness. Thus consciousness understood if there creates lives otherwise it becomes pseudo but working silently for the formation of our universes and then behaves like entanglement. Consciousness is, therefore, a non-material entity capable of independent, eternal existence, and not a property but in some sense may be used as property. Consciousness is not emergent, and is eternal similar to the electron. It can remain localized in the human brain and interact with the brain, and thereby, control the activities of the human body. While electrons in the brain behave as particles, these electrons prevent the consciousness from realizing that it is part of a larger whole. When the electrons behave as a wave, the consciousness becomes aware of its existence outside the human mind, which makes OBE and NDE possible. Whenever the electron wave function collapses, the OBE and NDE ends and the person returns to their physical body and its perception of reality similar to the collapsing of the wave function in the double slit experiment in quantum physics. During the OBE and NDE while the electron is behaving as a wave function, consciousness can leave the brain and go into an independent floating existence outside the human body where it can travel independent of space-time similar to the entangled electron.

How does the “I” or “self” or the perceived wholeness of one’s world emerge from a system consisting of so many parts, billions of neurons. What creates the “Oneness” of thought processes? What creates individuality and “I”-ness or “self”? What creates feelings, free will, and creativity? The problem is solved only by making a complete total body assumed like an atom/molecule with the combination of two different characters of electromagnetic wave functions producing in two different phases by the symmetry breaking of SU(11) & SU(5) and then formation of biological particles, otherwise does not create such feelings etc.

References

In Quantum Theory and Measurement, Wheeler, J. A., and Zurek, W. H. (eds), Princeton University Press, 1983; Originally in Reviews of Modern Physics, 29, 454. Engel, G.S., Calhoun, T.R., Read, E.L., Ahn, T-K., Mancal, T., Cheng, Y-C., Blankenship, R.E., Fleming, G.R.,

(2007). Evidence for wave-like energy transfer through quantum coherence in photo synthetic systems, Nature 446: 782. Bhadra N.K. (2012): The complex Model of the Universe, IOSR-JM, ISSN: 2278-5728, vol.2, 4, pp-20; and The complex model of the quantum universe, ISSN: 2278-5728.IOSR Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM) vol.4, Issue. 1(Nov.-Dec2012),pp-20. "The Complex Quantum-State of Black-Hole and Thermostatistics" (IOSR-JM: e-ISSN: 2278-3008, p-ISSN: 2319-7676. Volume 8, Issue 5 (Nov. –Dec. 2013), PP 01-19)].Bhadra NK; THE COMPLEX QUANTUM AND CLASSICAL PSEUDO-TACHYONIC UNIVERSE; (IOSR-JM) e-ISSN: 2278-5728,p-ISSN: 2319-765X, Volume 8, Issue 3 (Sep. -Oct. 2013. THE COMPLEX QUANTUM-STATE OF CONSCIOUSNESS, IOSR Journal of Applied Physics (IOSR-JAP) e-ISSN: 2278-4861.Volume 9, Issue 1 Ver. II (Jan. – Feb. 2017), PP 57-93 www.iosrjournals.org. The Origin of Consciousness in the Universe-IOSR Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM) e-ISSN: 2278-5728, p-ISSN: 2319-765X.Volume 10,Issue 5 Ver.III (Sep-Oct.2014),PP 53 68www.iosrjournals.orgwww.iosrjournals.org 53| Page.